

Determination of Oxalates by Oxidation with Non-Aqueous Iodine Solution

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A titrimetric method for the determination of oxalates has been described involving oxidation with iodine dissolved in carbon tetrachloride. The procedure is applicable for the evaluation of 5 to 40 mg. of oxalate ion with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$. With slight modification the proposed procedure can be adopted for estimating oxalates in presence of chloride ion.

THE reaction between oxalates and iodine is slow at ordinary temperature, but is accelerated under the influence of light¹. The quantitative oxidation of oxalates by iodine was achieved by Verma and Bose² by using a large excess of iodine, high temperature and prolonged heating. The study of this reaction was undertaken with a view to ascertain appropriate conditions for a rapid quantitative oxidation of oxalates. Dhar, Bhattacharya and Mukerji³ showed that potassium iodide retarded the reaction rate. Iodine was, therefore, dissolved in carbon tetrachloride instead of potassium iodide solution. The presence of iodide ion was thus avoided; this minimised considerably the time required for the complete oxidation of oxalates.

The procedure described in this communication consists of heating the neutral oxalate solution with an excess of saturated solution of iodine in carbon tetrachloride. The iodide ion formed during the reaction is decomposed with a known excess of potassium iodate solution and acid. After boiling off the liberated iodine, the residual iodate is determined iodometrically. Knowing the amount of iodate consumed, the quantity of iodide formed and hence the amount of oxalate ion present in the assay solution can be calculated. A blank is also run. The difference between the blank and the experimental titres gives the amount of iodate consumed in terms of thiosulphate solution used. The reactions involved are:

1 ml. of 0.1N thiosulphate corresponds to 3.6666 mg. of oxalate ion.

Experimental

Sodium oxalate, iodine and sodium thiosulphate used were of A. R. quality. Potassium iodide and potassium iodate were of E. Merck's variety. 0.1N potassium iodate, 10% potassium iodide, 1% starch, saturated solution of iodine in carbon tetrachloride, 0.1, 0.05 and 0.025N thiosulphate and 0.05, 0.01 and 0.005M sodium oxalate solutions were prepared.

Preliminary Experiments: Experiments were conducted to find out the suitable amount of iodine required for the complete oxidation of sodium oxalate. The results obtained have been presented in Table 1.

Effect of Increase in the Amount of Iodine on the Oxidation of Sodium Oxalate

(5 ml. of 0.05M sodium oxalate + 20 ml. water + varying volumes of iodine solution-I₂ boiled off + 15 ml. of 0.1N KIO₃ + 5 ml. of 2N. H₂SO₄ again iodine boiled off - cooled + 5ml. of 10% KI soln.-liberated iodine titrated with standard thiosulphate solution).

Table 1

Expt. No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ml. of iodine soln. added	2	5	10	15	20	30	40	50	60	70
% oxidation:	66.4	85.0	90.0	98.75	99.6	100.0	100.0	100.4	100.6	100.6

Note: Saturated solution of iodine was added gradually in instalments of 5 ml. each, addition in bulk causes waste of iodine as it boils off unreacted

From the above table it is evident that the addition of 20 to 50 ml. of iodine solution gives satisfactory results.

Procedure

To the given neutral oxalate solution (containing 4 to 40 mg of the oxalate ion) taken in a conical flask

20 ml. of water and 10 ml. of saturated solution of iodine in carbon tetrachloride are added. The conical flask is loosely covered by a glass stopper and is kept on a hot plate. When almost all the iodine boils off about 5 ml. of iodine solution is further added. In this way, in all 40 ml. of iodine solution is added and

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the mixture is heated till the iodine-colour disappears. A known volume of standard potassium iodate solution and 5 ml. of 2*N* sulphuric acid are then introduced into the flask and heating is continued till the liberated iodine is completely boiled off. This decomposes the iodide formed during the oxidation of the oxalate by iodine. The contents of the flask are then cooled, about 5ml. of 10% potassium iodide solution added and the liberated iodine is titrated with standard thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. A blank is also carried out. The difference between the blank and the experimental titres is equivalent to the amount of iodate consumed from which the quantity of oxalate ion present in the assay solution can be calculated. The results for the evaluation of various oxalate solutions presented in Table-2 show that the accuracy of the procedure is $\pm 0.5\%$ or better.

After the addition of about 100 ml. of iodine solution, a measured excess of iodate solution is introduced into the reaction mixture and benzoic acid gradually (about 0.1g. each time) added to the boiling reaction mixture till the liberation of iodine ceases (liberation of iodine is due to the reaction between iodide, formed during the oxidation, and iodate). At this stage about 0.5g. of benzoic acid is added as excess and heating is continued to drive off iodine completely. In all about 1g. of benzoic acid is added. The residual iodate is then determined iodometrically.

The results recorded in Table 3 show that the presence of potassium chloride upto 10g. does not interfere with the procedure. The error is upto 1% which is always on the negative side.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF SODIUM OXALATE

Mg. of Sodium Oxalate	Present-Found- % Error-	67.00, 66.72, 0.42,	50.25, 50.05, -0.40,	33.50, 33.43, -0.22,	26.80, 26.87, +0.25,	20.10, 20.03, -0.35,	13.40, 13.40, nil,	6.70 6.70 nil
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TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF SODIUM OXALATE IN PRESENCE OF POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

g. of KCl added		1.0 ,	2.0 ,	5.0 ,	8.0 ,	10.0 ,	10.0
mg. of sodium oxalate	Present-Found- % Error-	6.70, 6.66, -0.6	6.70, 6.66, -0.6	6.70, 6.64, -0.9	6.70, 6.64, -0.9	6.70, 6.64, -0.9	67.00 66.45 -0.83

Determination of oxalates in presence of potassium chloride :

Oxidimetric methods for the determination of oxalates employing potassium permanganate or trivalent manganese are interfered by the presence of chloride ions. The proposed procedure can be applied for the estimation of oxalates by making the following minor changes to the procedure described above.

1. When chloride ions are present, in all 100 ml. of saturated iodine solution in carbon tetrachloride should be added in order to accomplish quantitative oxidation of the oxalate solution. The iodine solution should be added gradually in instalments of 10 ml. each to the oxalate solution.

2. The iodide ion formed during the oxidation of the oxalate should be decomposed by iodate-benzoic acid mixture and not by iodate-sulphuric acid mixture as described previously.

In conclusion it is stated that the proposed method is rapid, simple and fairly accurate ; being iodometric the end-point is sharp. The advantage of the method is its applicability in presence of large amounts of chloride ions.

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References

1. W. V. BHAGWAT, Bull. Acad. Sci. United Provinces Agra Oudh, Allahabad, India, 1931-32, 1, 54 *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 649.
2. R. M. VERMA and SAMBER BOSE, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1963, 26, 122.
3. N. R. DHAR, A. K. BHATTACHARYA, and B. L. MUKHERJI, *Nature* 1933, 131, 840.